

WORK FAMILY FAIRNESS AND WORK FAMILY ENRICHMENT

Aneel Kumar^{*1}, Muhammad Waqas Maharvi²

^{*1}Associate Professor Institute of Commerce and Management Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur, Pakistan

²Assistant Professor Institute of Business, Management and Administrative Sciences The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Pakistan

^{*1}aneel.kumar@salu.edu.pk, ²waqas.maharvi@iub.edu.pk

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15679432>

Keywords

Distributive, procedural, interpersonal and informational justice; Work to family enrichment

Article History

Received on 07 May 2025

Accepted on 07 June 2025

Published on 17 June 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Aneel Kumar

Abstract

This study examined the effect of four forms of justice (i.e., distributive, procedural, interpersonal and informational justice) on work to family enrichment. This will help to understand the extent to which organizations are fair enough to take care of the social side of their employees and their policies, programs and procedures are not only for the work related role but providing them a fair deal which enables them to improve their family role as well. For this cross sectional type of research one time primary data were collected from the 210 lower level workers of wholesale dates market of Khairpur Mir's district of Pakistan through convenient sampling method. We found significant effect of all four forms of justice on work to family enrichment. Implications of this study for the workers of multiple firms are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

A rich amount of earlier literature can provide you insights on work family conflict (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985) and later after the emergence of work family enrichment theory (Greenhaus & Powell, 2006), positive side of both human roles has been talk of the town. This positive theory posits that resources generated in role A (i.e., work) improves performance in role B (i.e., family) and the vice versa. Carlson, et al. (2006) coined these two directions as the work to family enrichment and family to work enrichment. This study has focused on the former direction to investigate its implications in the organizational context. Work to family enrichment direction is related to resources acquired from workplace to improve performance in family role

(Carlson, et al., 2006). One of the important aspects which has been empirically investigated and found significant effect on the negative side (Judge & Colquitt, 2004) is different dimension of work family organizational justice i.e., distributive, procedural, interpersonal and informational (Judge & Colquitt, 2004). To contribute in the positive aspect of work family balance, this study intends to find the effect of these forms of organizational justice on work to family enrichment. Although, there are many resources which are not only been postulated in this theory but empirically tested as well such as supervisory support (Kumar, Channa, & Bhutto, 2017), flexible work arrangements (McNall, Masuda, & Nicklin, 2009), servant leadership (H. Zhang,

Kwong Kwan, Everett, & Jian, 2012), job resources (Y. Zhang, Lei, & Yang, 2025), work family policies (Martinez-Sanchez, Perez-Perez, Vela-Jimenez, & Abella-Garces, 2018) job autonomy (Jing, Li, Stanley, Guo, & Wenjing, 2021) but the extent to which these resources have fairly been offered by the organizations to their employees is hardly been investigated except a few studies which have focused on one or other form of justice such as distributive and procedural (Agrawal & Mahajan, 2023) but none of the studies have incorporated these four forms of justice and specifically in context of work family, it is rare to find any study. We argue that if organizations can fairly provide the work family resources to their employees then it will contribute not only to meet their work demands but their family role performance will also improve. Therefore, this study will help us to understand the extent to which organizations are fair enough to take care of the social side of their employees and their policies, programs and procedures are not only for the work related role but providing them a fair deal which enables them to improve their family role as well.

Literature Review

Initially, the concept of organizational justice was related to the perceived fairness of outcomes of the decision or the fairness of the treatment given to the employees in the workplace (i.e., distributive justice) and then another form which was related to perceived fairness of the procedures adopted in decision making (Colquitt, 2001). Further, building on the premises of Greenberg (1993), Colquitt (2001) developed and validated a four factor model of organizational justice. Later, Judge & Colquitt (2004) incorporated these four forms in context of work family conflict. One of these forms of organization justice is distributive justice which is related to the extent to which the work family policies and programs are perceived as fair by the employees; second is procedural justice which deals with the procedures followed in work family policies and programs; third is interpersonal justice which is related to sincerity and respect offered in treatment; fourth is informational justice which is related to either these policies has fairly been explained to employees or not (Judge & Colquitt, 2004). Later on most common two forms of justice (i.e., distributive

and procedural) been empirically been investigated either in context of work family conflict (Kumar, Arain, & Channa, 2019) or work family enrichment (Agrawal & Mahajan, 2023), however, the empirical investigation to understand the effects of these four forms of justice in context of work to family enrichment are scant. Further, Khilji (2013) reported that employees have a little role to play in the polices due to centralized structure and still the HR systems have not been properly implemented. Instead of their organizations, workers relay on their colleagues and families for help. It will be interesting to examine that how fair these policies are, keeping in mind the family role of workers. Therefore, this study has proposed to empirical investigate these four forms in context of work to family enrichment.

H1: Four forms of work family related organizational justice (i.e., i.e., distributive, procedural, interpersonal and informational) will engender the work to family enrichment experiences positively.

Method

Sample

For this cross sectional type of research one time primary data were collected from the lower level workers of wholesale dates market of Khairpur Mir's district of Pakistan. As the total population was unknown and we only came to know about it when we personally visited the firms and distributed around 250 questionnaires through convenient sampling method. Out of 250, we included 210, properly filled for this study.

Measure

The four dimension of organizational justice were measured through a five point Likert scales adopted from the study of Judge & Colquitt (2004). A four items scale of distributive justice, a seven item's scale of procedural justice, a four item's scale of interpersonal justice and a five item's scale of informational justice were adopted. Work to family enrichment was measured by 9 item's scale adopted from Carlson, et al. (2006). Based on several past studies, age and experience were included as the controls.

Analysis Techniques

Multiple regression analyses (Hair, Black, Babin, & Anderson, 2010) were performed to test the propositions through SPSS.

Results

After the preliminary data screening tests (Pallant, 2020), reliabilities and descriptive statistics results

were determined, which are given in table 1. Reliability of all variables was within acceptable minimum level of .7 (Hair, et al., 2010). The mean fairness perceptions of workers revealed just slight agreement and similarly, their mean level of work to family enrichment was also average.

Table 1: Mean, Standard Deviation and Reliability

S. No.	Variable	M	S.D	α
1.	Age	25.06	2.50	----
2.	Experience	03.02	1.69	----
3.	Distributive Justice	03.33	.72	.85
4.	Procedural Justice	03.83	.77	.91
5.	Interpersonal Justice	03.55	.85	.86
6.	Informational Justice	03.76	.76	.85
7.	Work to Family Enrichment	03.34	.72	.83

Note: M = Mean; α = Cronbach’s Alpha; S.D= Standard Deviation; N= 210

Correlations between all the forms of justice i.e., distributive (r =.48, p < .00), procedural (r =.63, p < .00), interpersonal (r =.42, p < .00) and

informational (r =.46, p < .00) and dependent variable (i.e., work to family enrichment) were positive and significant as we proposed.

Table 2: Correlations

S. No.	Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1.	Age	1						
2.	Experience	.55**	1					
3.	Distributive Justice	.06	.09	1				
4.	Procedural Justice	.04	.03	.39**	1			
5.	Interpersonal Justice	-.04	.00	.37**	.38**	1		
6.	Informational Justice	-.01	.04	.34**	.40**	.03	1	
7.	Work to Family Enrichment	.03	.06	.48**	.63**	.42**	.46**	1

Note: N= 210; p-value < .01

Our model showed significant fit as model explained a significant variance of around 52%. Further, we found significant effect of distributive (β = .16, p< .01), procedural (β = .37, p< .01), interpersonal (β = .16, p< .01) and informational (β = .22, p< .01)

justice and work to family enrichment. Therefore, our proposition H1 can’t be rejected. The role of controls on dependent measures was also insignificant as regressions as well as correlations showed.

Table 3: Regression Effects

Independent Variables	β	Std. Error	t	p
Age	.00	.02	.06	.95
Experience	.01	.03	.39	.69
Distributive Justice	.16	.06	2.9	.00
Procedural Justice	.37	.05	6.7	.00
Interpersonal Justice	.16	.04	3.4	.00

Informational Justice	.22	.05	4.2	.00
-----------------------	-----	-----	-----	-----

Dependent Variable: Work to Family Enrichment; R = .72; R-Square = .52; p-value < .01

Discussion

In this research, we addressed the role of fair work family related policies and programs in engenders the work family enrichment among the workers of various firms. The initial mean fairness perception showed a slight fairness either it is for the procedures involved, providing the due sympathy or concern or for the explanation to make them aware about policies and specifically for the distributive, their perceptions were just average. Further, for enrichment experiences, workers' perceptions were also average. These results shows that workers have a little role to play as Khilji (2013) reported that employees have a little role to play in the polices due to centralized structure and still the HR systems have not been properly implemented. Instead of their organizations, workers relay on their colleagues and families for help. Further, as the results revealed, for distributive justice, if the work family policies (distributive justice) are fair according to the perception of workers then these are likely to provide gains of work to family enrichment. The role of procedures adopted in the development of such policies and programs also showed significant effect. The effect of interpersonal fairness of treatment given to employees by the authority involved in development of these polices was also significant. Further, proper communication of these polices to employees also showed significant effect in enhancing work to family enrichment of workers. These results are also consistent with the limited evidence available for effect of some forms of justice (i.e., distributive and procedural) (Agrawal & Mahajan, 2023) on work to family enrichment.

Managerial Implications

Implications of this study for the workers of multiple firms are discussed. As the results showed that the fairness perception of workers plays a significant role for the development of work to family enrichment experiences. The workers under study have very unique work schedule. In the peak season, they work throughout the day with little breaks and in the off season they have a very little work to do. Therefore,

scheduling their work family policies is an uphill task. Authorities involved in development of these policies should make sure that these are fair enough according to employees work family role and the procedures adopted are also fair enough. Further, authorities should also make sure that these policies are effectively explained and communicated to workers with care concern and in a respectful manner.

Limitations and Future Directions

This study has determined only main effects, therefore incorporating social support from the work place (i.e., supervisory/ coworkers) as moderator can extend this study. Similarity, the work to family enrichment experiences of workers can have a significant effect on attitudes and behaviors of workers; therefore, it can be tested as mediator. The demographic factor (i.e., gender) was constant as all the workers were male; therefore a diverse sample with female workers can provide a diversified picture. It is a type of first study which have incorporated all the four forms and specifically for work family concerns. Therefore, further testing for generalizations are recommended.

REFERENCES

- Agrawal, M., & Mahajan, R. (2023). The influence of distributive and procedural justice on work-family conflict, enrichment, and mental health of Indian police. *Police Practice and Research*, 24(2), 245-265.
- Carlson, D. S., Kacmar, K. M., Wayne, J. H., & Grzywacz, J. G. (2006). Measuring the positive side of the work-family interface: Development and validation of a work-family enrichment scale. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 68(1), 131-164.
- Colquitt, J. A. (2001). On the dimensionality of organizational justice: a construct validation of a measure. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 86(3), 386.

- Greenberg, J. (1993). The social side of fairness: Interpersonal and informational classes of organizational justice. *Justice in the workplace: Approaching fairness in human resource management*, Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Hillsdale, NJ.
- Greenhaus, J. H., & Beutell, N. J. (1985). Sources of conflict between work and family roles. *Academy of Management Review*, 10(1), 76-
- Greenhaus, J. H., & Powell, G. N. (2006). When work and family are allies: A theory of work-family enrichment. *Academy of Management Review*, 31(1), 72-92.
- Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson, R. E. (2010). *Multivariate data analysis* (7 ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Jing, S., Li, Z., Stanley, D. M., Guo, X., & Wenjing, W. (2021). Work-family enrichment: influence of job autonomy on job satisfaction of knowledge employees. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 726550.
- Judge, T. A., & Colquitt, J. A. (2004). Organizational Justice and Stress: The Mediating Role of Work-Family Conflict. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 89(3), 395-404. doi: 10.1037/0021-9010.89.3.395
- Khilji, S. E. (2013). Human resource management in Pakistan. In P. S. Budhwar & Y. A. Debrah (Eds.), *Human resource management in developing countries* (pp. 102-120): London: Routledge.
- Kumar, A., Arain, G. A., & Channa, K. A. (2019). Relationship Between Organizational Injustice and Work Interference with Family: The Role of Social Support. *South Asian Journal of Human Resources Management*, 6(2), 129-155. doi: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/2322093719828889>
- Kumar, A., Channa, K. A., & Bhutto, N. A. (2017). Gender as Moderator of the Relationship between Supervisory Support and Work to Family Enrichment. *Global Management Journal for Academic & Corporate Studies*, 7(1), 103-109.
- Martinez-Sanchez, A., Perez-Perez, M., Vela-Jimenez, M.J., & Abella-Garces, S. (2018). Job satisfaction and work-family policies through work-family enrichment. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 33(4/5), 386-402.
- McNall, L. A., Masuda, A. D., & Nicklin, J. M. (2009). Flexible work arrangements, job satisfaction, and turnover intentions: The mediating role of work-to-family enrichment. *The Journal of Psychology*, 144(1), 61-81.
- Pallant, J. (2020). *SPSS survival manual: A step by step guide to data analysis using IBM SPSS* (7 ed.): Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003117452>.
- Zhang, H., Kwong Kwan, H., Everett, A. M., & Jian, Z. (2012). Servant leadership, organizational identification, and work to family enrichment: The moderating role of work climate for sharing family concerns. *Human Resource Management*, 51(5), 747-767.
- Zhang, Y., Lei, S., & Yang, F. (2025). Relationship between Job Resources and Job Embeddedness among Tertiary-level Public Hospital Nurses: Parallel Mediating Roles of Work-Family Conflict and Work-Family Enrichment. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 13, 1527511.